

INTERROGATING CHANGE IN THE INDIGENOUS INSTITUTIONS AND PROCESSES OF CONFLICT RESOLUTION IN IGBO TRADITIONAL SOCIETIES OF NIGERIA

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Abstract

The paper explores change in the indigenous institutions and processes of conflict resolution in Igbo traditional societies of Nigeria. It stresses the effects of alien institutions on traditional institutions and processes of conflict resolution, in the same vein. It also identifies counter-forces that resisted change from these alien institutions and processes of conflict resolution from over-running traditional system. The paper adopted historical method of content and qualitative analysis of primary and secondary sources. The findings of this paper revealed among others that strong institutional base, effective resolution implementation machineries' and cost effective processes account for the ability of the indigenous to resist the forces of change brought by alien institutions. It concluded with the view that the core traditional institutions and processes of conflict resolution have remained resilient to change because the forces of change through alien institutions and processes have some deficiencies.

Keywords: Change, Continuity, Conflict Resolution, Traditional Institutions, Aliens

Introduction

The paper discusses reaction of indigenous institutions and processes of conflict resolution in Igbo matrilineal traditional societies of Nigeria and their contact with foreign institutions and processes of conflict resolution since colonial period. A community is a traditional society if its characteristics include compact relationship, strong allegiance to custom, continuum in tradition with little change from generation to generation and strong kinship ties. The traditional societies under consideration are Abiriba, Abam, Afipko and Amasiri in Cross River Igbo in Nigeria. These communities share some common characteristics which include: organized age grade system, situated in the same geographical area and practices matrilineal family system. There were both internal and external dynamics that accounted for the change and resilience of these traditional institutions and processes of conflict resolution. The issue of social-cultural change and continuity as a result of alien institutions intrusion into Igbo land for a long time has continued to generate debate among scholars. Some of these scholars have argued that the introduction of alien institutions and processes of conflict resolution in Igbo land led to the extinction of indigenous processes, while other scholars on the contrary opine that the introduction tried to undermine the traditional processes but were undermined by forces inherent in them. However Adiele Afigbo asserts that the introduction of alien system purged the indigenous processes of anti-human or barbaric tendencies.¹ This is in agreement with the view of missionaries, Christian converts and some educated people interviewed in the course of the study.

This discussion revolves around the view of people who think that the intrusion of alien institutions and processes have undermined the traditional ones and those who think otherwise. These opposing views will be weighed in the light of historical findings of the traditional institutions and processes of conflict resolution, with that

alien's counterparts. Change is constant phenomenon in human societies and activities. It is a product of both internal external forces such as discontentment with the old ways of doing things, education and Christianity, migration and physical forces. These force of change run through the indigenous institutions, traditions and cultures of the people not without restrictions from within these traditional societies or from outside. Study has shown that counter-force in indigenous institutions and processes resisted major aspects of change and kept the continuum of the indigenous processes of conflict resolution. These counter-forces among others are strong institutional base, ritualism and timely resolution of conflict at minimal cost.² The thesis statement of this paper is to explore the extent of change and continuity in the traditional institutions and processes of conflict resolution among some Cross River Igbo communities. In pursuance of the foregoing the following were examined; it examines change in contextual analysis; interrogates forces of change against traditional institutions and processes of conflict resolution and factors of resilient against the change driven by aliens' institutions.

Change in contextual analysis

Change is continuous occurrence in every society. Some are fast in happening while others appear to be slow even unnoticeable. The extent of change that has taken place in indigenous processes of conflict resolution are such that appears in all fabrics of the society either overt or overt. Oran Young rightly avers that "like all social institutions, governance system... once establishment, they change continually in a variety of ways."³ The driven forces and resilient forces against change in these communities under review are the focus of this discussion. It is obvious that the opposing social systems which tried to dominate in these communities were tradition, alien religious belief especially Christian teachings, the modern justice system and education. Each of these impinged on the other and termed it superior, evil, or primitive by the people under study. It is worthy to emphasis that all these camp directed their attacks towards traditional institutions and system of conflict resolution. The traditional processes of conflict resolution, witnessed external force that attempted to change them. G. Walker, et al, remark that:

societies changed or transformed fundamentally when certain social and ecological system trapped in a highly resistant state or that uncertainly in the environment forced social systems and institutions to become open to influence and consequently adapted such changes which were deemed valuable and compliant with their traditional system for the well-being of their people.⁴

Evidence in support of this assertion can be found in the practice of human sacrifice, selling into slavery and trail by ordeal. These communities used these processes for conflict resolution but these practices have changed. For example, the use of human sacrifice had been replaced by animal sacrifice, while act of selling into slavery has gone into extinction. In the same vein, the process of robbing pepper in the eyes of deviant children by Udamini Ufuforo [a juvenile and feminine deity] has also changed to fine.⁵

G. Handmer and S. Doves, opine that "changes are caused are caused by shifts in the ecological and social systems; and changes which resulted to shifts in the collective choices of formal and informal rules by the people."⁶ In the Cross River Igbo, the force of colonialism, education, migration and urbanization were responsibility for such change. The pattern of change in the processes of conflict

resolution among these communities involved subtle and covert change within the traditional framework of norms and values. However, although the processes undergo slight changes but much did not change in the institutions of conflict resolution irrespective of these force of change. For Instance, following Chidiebere onouha's grouped traditional institutions into two major categories, one is the nature institutions [institutions which evolved with the people as they settled in their respective communities], they are made up of the family, compound elder, kens groups, village court, communal court and the oracles. Two , the auxiliary institutions these are institutions formed by these communities because of the exigencies of the period. They include the age grades, market court and the guilds. It is interesting to emphasize that none of these institutions have gone into extinction or changed as the study reveals. The only exception of this is the Anohia [one of the villages that make up Afipko scenario from 1957, this village witnessed a fundamental change which affected all the institutions and processes of not only conflict resolution but of every other tradition and culture of this village.⁷ It is interesting to state that the force of change in this village was neither Christianity nor education. Rather, it was Islam, which drove this wheel of change. The change was possible because of the discontentment which the people had no their culture and tradition and were in great need of change. This trend in this village agrees with Gupta et al view that:

Trapped in a highly resistant or that uncertainty in the environment forced social system and institutions to become open to influences and consequently adapted such changes which were deemed valuable and compliant with their traditional system for the well being of their people.⁸

This statement played out in this village, when the opportunity for change provided itself true one of their sons okpani egwani (known as alhaji ibraham) that converted into islam they seized it. In fact, the villagers through the directives of this their son destroyed their shrines and converted to Islam. This is the only place where internal and external forces worked together and enthroned change. From 1957 till date the people of this village has remained Muslims. It was a radical change which led to what the author termed traditional institutions, cultural and belief system paradigm shift.

Forces of Change Against Traditional Institutions and Processes of Conflict Resolution

Change is constant in life, in every culture or community. It usually happened when there is contact either from internal or external culture influences. Mead avers that:

The condition for change, although hidden, is always present, even when traditional procedures are merely repeated. There is always a possibility that some previously accepted procedure, custom or belief will be questioned. This chance increases when the people of one ... culture are in close contact with those of another. Such contact sharpens their sense of what constitutes their own culture.⁹

This is a fact, covert, or gradual change is constant. In the Cross River Igbo communities under study, the changes in the indigenous processes of conflict resolution were brought about by the following external factors.

Christianity and Education: The twin's institutions of Christianity and Education were the major forces of change against the indigenous institutions and their processes of resolving conflict. The incursion of Christianity from 1901 into Cross River Igbo communities influenced and in most cases changed some processes of conflict

resolution especially the verdict options. It is worthy of note that Christian denominations came with easier, none cost and humane processes of conflict resolution against what obtained before its advent. For instance, the Christian doctrine of forgiveness and reconciliation, and free processes of conflict resolution processes tried to undermine those of the indigenous institutions which charged little fees for such. In addition, the constant condemnations of some of the traditional processes of conflict resolution by the Christians denominations such as the consultation of the oracles, the practices of oath taking, and covenant making grossly influenced the indigenous and also set some natives against the institutions and processes that the previously believed and submitted to. Even though these communities had their misgiving about the Christian mission but the perceived gains that were expected to accrue from their accommodation overruled other fears. In agreement with the foregoing, Adiele Afigbo opines that:

Through the schools the missions exploited to some advantage the burning desire of the Igbo to become as expert as the British in the manipulation of their physical world. In effect the Igbo were not converted to Christianity, they were ensnared.¹⁰

This assertion is correct because the people were ensnared by education. For example, in 1905, the Scotland Missionary Society [SMS] now Presbyterian Church [SMS] now Presbyterian Church requested the people of Abiriba to grant them the permission to open a mission in their community but they refused. The reason for their refusal is that the "Church people" were trouble makers capable of destroyed their tradition. However, in 1910 after prolonged persuasion the people granted them the permission and the SMS opened a mission post. Furthermore, in 1911, the SMS also requested for permission to open a school in the community but the people refused. It took the effort of a native of Abiriba known as Agwu Otisi [a native of Abiriba] convince his community to allow the Church and Education institutions to co-exist. He explained to his people what they stand to gain if the school is established. As a trader at Eniong [presently in Calabar] he witnessed instances where liberated people read letters and he felt that he must do something to bring his people to that level of civilization. When the SMS made the request to establish a Christian mission in Abiriba, he summoned his people at Agboji [one of the three major communities of Abiriba] and narrated to them the advantages of having both the church and the school. He stressed that if they make the mistake of not allowing their children to be educated, that their children in future world find it difficult to match their counterparts from neighbouring communities; He further told them that they would even stand the risk of being deprived of their farmlands by the peoples of other communities who acquired the 'magic' of education. This presentation destroyed the iron bar of resistance and forced the Ekpe (a cultural group) to provide the counterpart funding of twenty dollars needed for the establishment of the school.¹¹ The establishment of the mission schools brought education to the people, and gave them the knowledge to challenge the indigenous processes of conflict resolution. This scenario was common among the Cross River Igbo communities. From 1901 to 1924 as a result of gain that would accrue from the accommodation of education, Christianity and its culture spread in the area and influenced the traditional cultures.

Modern law Enforcement Agencies: The modern institutions such as police, the modern courts and the Army, had great influence on the indigenous institutions and processes of conflict resolution. The modern courts started as native courts started as native courts in the Cross River Igbo area from 1902. The establishment of courts

followed a successful military expedition against ibini-ukpabi oracle in 1901 of Arochukwu. The need to ensure that the people would not consult the oracle gave impetus to the establishment of modern courts. The courts from its inception had government mercenaries to mobilize force and ensure compliance in conflict resolution. It was a paradigm shift from the indigenous conflict resolution institutions and processes. The court, for instance, introduced prison sentencing, payment of heavy fines and public execution of offenders. It also introduced extortions in the traditional institutions and processes of conflict resolution. The community elders that saw the processes of peace making as selfless sacrifice and community service developed the habit of charging fees or other inducement before resolving conflict. The modern law enforcement agencies process of conflict resolution altered the indigenous pertains. The indigenous institutions of conflict resolution experienced a counter resolution systems which forced them to adapt to some of the modern courts processes. A good example is that of Afikpo traditional court that they restructured their traditional court with some practices of the modern court.¹²

Migration and Urbanization: The twins phenomena of migration and urbanization influenced the operation of indigenous institutions and processes of conflict resolution. Migration naturally uprooted mostly the young and able-bodied people from these communities under study to a distance lands in search of greener pasture. The resultant effect of migrations was the reduction of the numerical strength, which in turn affected the indigenous law enforcement agencies, such as the age grades. These were three major waves of migrations witnessed among the Cross River Igbo. The first wave started from the second decade of the twentieth century which was occasioned by discovery of coal in Enugu in 1909. The second was the construction Enugu-Portharcourt Railway from 1913. This labour activity, forced Cross River Igbo people to Enugu, Otukpo, Ovim, Uzuakoli, Isuikwuato Umuahia. Aba and portharcourt. The third was as a result of the Nigerian civil war and its aftermath.

This is not to state that there were no other forms of migration outside these waves, there were, but low in dimension comparing to this one. The opening up of urban centers in Calabar, Enugu, portharcourt, and Umuahia and Aba continually attracted migrants from these communities. Consequently, the migrants become acculturate and also transferred the newly acquired cultures into their various communities. Afigbo observes that “in these [urban] centers Igbo elements found themselves compelled to adopt styles quit different from what they came with from the villagers. Of course, in the process of transferring the economic goods which was the expectancy of the indigenous communities, they also transfer some of the culture they have acquired. Some of these transferred cultures were attending church services; the use of police and the courts, to resolve conflicts. Consequently, these adopted and transferred cultures, strengthened the alien institutions, such as the faith based institutions, the police and the court. In the same vein, they also transformed the indigenous institutions and practice of conflict resolution in the communities. In other words, these returnees’ migrants served as agents of institutional and cultural transformation and change.”¹³

Factors of Resilient Against Change Driven by Aliens’ Institutions

Irrespective of the alien forces of change, most of the traditional institutions and processes of conflict resolution remained resilient owing to some factors, However, On the contrary, Elijah Obinna has argued that “Igbo indigenous institution were mere house of cards which collapsed at the instance of change brought about by this alien forces.”¹⁴This argument is faulty as the study carried out on this issue has

proven. This is because the core indigenous institutions and processes of conflict resolution among the Cross River Igbo were used both during the colonial and post-colonial periods in these communities. Even the oracles that were outlawed during the colonial period regained relevance during the early colonial period from 1901-1930. This happened because of the inherent strength of the traditional institutions and processes of conflict resolution. C. Gupta et al, describes the conditions necessary for transformation and continuity to be adjudged to exist when they remark that “the informal institutions, such as the traditional mores, oral lore and myths were able to withstand the disruptive influences introduced from outside the homeland of any area of study.”¹⁵ In the Cross River Igbo societies some of the things listed by Guta et al also played major roles.

The factors that accounted for the resilience of the indigenous process of conflict resolution are:

Strong Institutional Base: The resilience of the traditional institutions and processes of conflict resolution resided in its strong institutions. These institutions are: the family, the compound elders, the lineage groupings, the village assembly, the King’s court and the supernatural court. In these communities the people were not only close to these institutions but were highly represented by members to their families. This crosscutting membership was and still is the base of the strong traditional institutions. These institutions were seen as such that every member of the communities had strong stake in them, In addition of the laws in which they operated were collectively made. The people and these institutions were closed knitted and this social organic character explains the emphasis on consensus of law and morals, conciliation and reinforcement of social solidarity. Thus, with this knowledge of collective enactment and ownership of law, all and sundry strive to respect both these institutions and its processes of conflict resolution.

Nature of conflict Resolution Institutions and processes: Another source of strength of the indigenous institutions and processes of conflict resolution among Cross River Igbo are medication, negotiation, conciliation, reconciliation and mass participation. Parties were also free to express their position without intimidation. Disputants receive immediate attention when aggrieved and resolution of issues were paramount for all. The goal is conciliation which enhanced restoration of peace and harmony with the individuals, groups or communities. In addition, conflict was resolved in a manner that did not undermine with the community’s shared values or ultimately endanger any possibility of re-establishing of harmonious coexistence in the future. It has been argued that this communal objective in conflict resolution is tantamount to suppression of justice because the parties in dispute must abide by the resolution of the institutions. More so, that because of communal principles conflict resolved festers and could be revived given the slightest opportunity. On the contrary, during the pre-colonial period to this present era, there were options such as oracular summon open to individuals who felt shortchanged in justice to explore for redress. The widening of the scope of conflict resolution did not undermine the traditional processes of conflict resolution.¹⁶

Government factor: The change of attitude by the government and its agencies to refer issues to the traditional institutions for resolution. This also gave more power or credence to indigenous institutions and process to be resilient to change. To say that colonial court did not understand that power of justice inherent in the traditional system is to misrepresent the facts. This is because most of the court functionaries such as clerks and messengers were from other Igbo communities and also

understand the importance of these institutions. Secondly, the loophole created by language barrier was well maximized to their benefits. Thirdly, the colonial administrations were not interested to encourage the traditional institutions as they view such as capable of undermine their authority on the people. These explained why they relegated it to the background, an action which they later regretted. In 1929, Lawrence Secretary Southern province remarks that:

It is probably that the intelligence reports will indicate the wisdom of paying closer and more sympathetic attention on the old social and religious institutions and sanctions such as clubs, religious heads, private oaths and sanctions, usually characterized by juju and many others: which have so frequently been ignored by officers as useless, evil and out of date.¹⁷

The implication of this realization is that the colonial administration changed their strategy in the course of time and allowed the oath-taking to be used in the native courts. However, the change of policy was not implemented in the Cross River Igbo communities, as the colonial officials feared that such oracular involvement will receive the *Ibini-Ukpabi oracle*. They erroneously believed that *Ibini-Ukpabi* control all the oracles in the area. A District reported that they have received the used of oath to prove guilt or innocent during native court session. Even in the post-colonial period some court judges came to terms with the reality that the modern courts lacks the capacity to resolve some inter personal and social conflict. This is evident by issues referred by the government and its agencies to the traditional courts. For instance, in 1980, Ugwube Oko, petitioned the Afikpo Local Government Area Secretary to intervene in an issue. Consequently, the secretary referred the matter to Omaka Ejali of Afikpo and his council of chiefs for amicable settlement. Another example is a land dispute originally started in 1984 as a criminal case of Afikpo, the chief Magistrate also referred the same to Omaka Ejali of Afikpo and his council of chiefs for resolution. The court and the police made the referrals of matters from the community as deliberate policies. This is because after resolving the matter through the government instruments the conflict to reverberate. Issues like this gave credence to the traditional processes and the power to resist change.¹⁸

Restorative Justice: The cost River Igbo communities practiced restorative justice in conflict resolution. Gordon Bazemore and Lode walgrave define restorative justice process as “when victims, offenders and other stakeholders meet face-to-face to resolve their conflict.¹⁹ This view does not connote the full meaning of restorative justice from traditional perspective From traditional perspective it involves not only to bring the stake holders of the conflict to the resolution table but also to resolve issue in such a way that the victim is not short-changed and the offenders is not alienated from the social circle. In other words, it seeks to resolve conflict and restore estranged relationship among the people. In fact, restorative justice system is characterized by justice, humane processes, social solidarity and acknowledgement of guilty by the offenders. Similarly, among the Cross River Igbo communities, the victims, offenders and other stake holders such as the witnesses, concerned observes and the gods always converge to resolve conflict. This is geared towards the satisfaction of all parties of conflict. It was essential to the restoration of peace and order in the community. The indigenous processes of conflict resolution were human centered and emphasized social solidarity. M. Iro describes Igbo societies thus:

Humane living according to him is a “way of life emphatically centered upon human interests and values, a mode of living evidently characterized by

empathy, and by consideration and compassion for human beings..... Igbo humanities is deeply ingrained in the traditional belief that the human being is supreme in the creation, is the greatest asset one can possess.²⁰

This is reflected in its treatment of offenders, efforts were made not to alienate the offender by excessive punishment. The offender expresses remorse, shame and reparation. Some offenses demand expiation ceremonies as part of the general healing process of the victim, the offender and the entire community. This restorative justice element in traditional processes of conflict resolution endears the natives to their institutions and processes.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the study explored Christianity and education, modern law enforcement agencies, migration and urbanization as forces of change against the institutions and the processes of conflict resolution among the Cross River Igbo communities. In the same vein, it discussed the nature of traditional institutions and processes of conflict resolution, strong institutional base among others as factors that resisted change from internal forces and alien institutions. However, while their factors played significant roles for or against change, there were other underlying forces that resisted change. The paper in consideration of the foregoing, states that most of the alien institutions and process introduced in the area operated in similar fashion like the traditional ones. For instance, the means of initiating conflict resolution processes through the alien institutions followed the same processes like the traditional system. The law enforcement agencies with its instrument of coercion to justice enforcement became so corrupt and time exhaustive venture, and also their inability to resolve to resolve conflict as they usually refer back the matter to these communities or families to resolve after exporting them. These made the police and the court to lose its strengths for justice and also discouraged the people to go with the change it brought. Furthermore, Christianity with its message of reconciliation and forgiveness was appealing to the people. However, the makeup of the converts such as the poor, social downtrodden and the antagonist posture of these converts alienated them from the institutions of these communities.

In addition, adherences of Christianity were always in conflict with members of the communities or with the communities. Education would have effected fundamental change but failed due to the level of illiteracy and entrenched superstition among the people. Migration and urbanization tried very much to change social life in dressing but not these institutions and processes because the migrant communities were very few and only spent few days when they visited their communities. Consequently, these salient issues gave no room or major change to take place in the traditional institutions and processes of conflict resolution. It is safer to say that these alien institutions and their system of conflict resolution only influenced or refined the indigenous ones. But radical change like what happened at Aniha Village was never seen in these communities. On this note the paper posits that one important observation is that for total change to occur in traditional institutions, there have to be co-operation between the custodians of this institutions and the alien agents of change.

ENDNOTES

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